

USE OF FOLK'S ORAL CREATION IN MORAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

Karimova Nafisa Saidullayevna

2nd stage graduate student of Tashkent International

University of Chemistry

Abstract: One of the important tasks facing primary education is to improve the methods of providing spiritual and moral education to primary school students. This article reflects on the role of the family in the effective use of folklore in providing moral education to elementary school students, and the role of the family in making them become well-rounded people in the future.

Key words: Ethics, folklore, spiritual and moral education, means of moral education, mental education, methods of moral education.

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, philosophers, scientists, parents, writers and teachers have been interested in the issue of moral education of the next generation. Let's not hide that each older generation determines that the moral foundations of the youth have declined. New recommendations are being developed regularly, their purpose is to increase the level of morals. Moral education is an important component of comprehensive development of the personality. It is a process aimed at inculcating moral ideas and knowledge in children, raising moral feelings and qualities of a person, positive attitudes and culture of behavior in them.

The word ethics comes from the Latin word "myeros", which means moral, logic, and it is a social law that is not strictly written down anywhere. If morality exists as a person's inner world, beliefs, and qualities, it is manifested in a person's conspicuous manners, behavior, and dealings. The level of formation of moral

concepts at different ages

Moral consciousness

Moral values

Moral feelings

Hossein Koshifi's "Ethics of Muhsini" contains the foundations of personal, family and civil ethics. Moral problems, socio-philosophical issues are analyzed in Jalaluddin Davani's work "Ethics of Jalali". Ahmad Yugnaki's work "Hibbat-ul-haqqayiq" was written in an educational and moral direction. In the chapter entitled "Truthfulness" of Abdulla Awlani's book "Turkiy Gulistan Yakhud Akhlaq", he considers truthfulness and truthfulness to be one of the most human qualities of a person. In Alisher Navoi's work "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" ideas about manners and ethics are put forward.

The main tasks of moral education are:

Education of moral feelings, ideas and behavior in children.

Educating a culture of behavior and positive relationships.

Cultivation of moral feelings in a person.

Elimination of negative feelings in behavior.

The task and content of moral education is performed based on the basic principles of moral education in kindergarten and compliance with pedagogical conditions. Its principles have been developed in accordance with the task and content of moral education for elementary school students. Moral education is an important component of all-round development of personality. It is a process aimed at inculcating moral ideas and knowledge in children, educating them about moral feelings and qualities of a person, positive attitudes and national culture. Imparting moral knowledge fulfills several educational tasks, a broad idea about the moral values of human life and culture, gives insights. Ethical imaginations affect the formation of concepts such as views, judgments, evaluations and, on this basis, increase moral beliefs. The main principles of moral education:

1. The educational work on ethics is aimed at a certain goal;
2. To approach the work of education while respecting the personality of the child;
3. Carrying out the work of moral education together with life and land;
4. Activity of children;
5. Team training.

Methods of moral education:

Group 1. Methods aimed at forming moral consciousness, moral imagination and knowledge, and the desire to fulfill them.

Group 2. Cultural behavior, methods aimed at forming positive relations.

Group 3. Auxiliary methods aimed at stimulating moral feelings and relationships.

Methods of formation of moral awareness: a) story b) explanation c) aesthetic conversation d) interpretation e) advice-training f) instruction g) example.

"Each person's peace in the world is education, happiness is the place of Iqbal's happiness - education. Fathers, your dearest children, be diligent, immortal time and time is education!! Abdulla Avloni.

The role of the educational process in the development of society is extremely incomparable. The thinker scientist Abu Nasir Farabi believes that the main task of education is to educate a mature person who can meet the demands of society and serve this society. It is necessary to educate a person who occupies an important place in the development of society, to encourage him to learn, to work, and to gradually turn this act into a skill. Man's observation cultivates the faculty and develops the mind. Mind preserves consciousness. Consciousness becomes a material and spiritual resource. In this way, a person gradually improves and reaches perfection. but for this, it requires long-term responsibility, honorable work, diligence and will from educators and students. It is necessary

for the teacher to take into account the age characteristics of the children. The environment and attitude in the family, surroundings, and society play an important role in the formation of spiritual and human qualities. Due to the imitability of children, the consciousness, spirituality, knowledge and education of parents are important in raising them. The effectiveness of education aimed at a specific goal depends on the method used by the educator.

The method, that is, the method, depending on the nature of information transmission and reception:

The method of expression through words.

Demonstration method.

Practical sample method.

It is divided into incentive and punishment methods.

These methods are divided into the following groups.

The first group is verbal transmission, giving advice, receiving information by hearing, story, lecture, conversation and other methods.

The second group - movies, fine arts, fine arts and other visual education methods.

The third group is to teach aspects of education through practical labor actions, to set an example, to show the work of others as an example.

The fourth group is approving well-done work in front of comrades, expressing gratitude, economic and moral encouragement.

Punishment is a confession of the child's wrongdoing.

Education is the process of imparting to others the positive skills of the lessons and intellectual potential of every person during his life.

Education is the ability to obey the moral norms accepted in society and refrain from actions that provoke the hatred of others.

Beruni emphasizes that while science, enlightenment, art and practice play a major role in a person's maturation, lineage, social environment and life rules are

also of great importance. In his opinion, the most important factors of human maturity are knowledge, enlightenment and high morality. The signs of morality are goodness, correctness, justice, humility, generosity, nobility, friendship and cooperation, hard work, purity, striving for beauty. Samples of Uzbek folk art are our priceless heritage, passed from generation to generation for centuries, updated and expressing the national culture and spirituality in their content. That is why the following words of the head of our country Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev in our republic:

"We have an enviable history. We have great ancestors who spoke enviably about employees of creative organizations, writers, and artists. We have immeasurable riches to covet. And I believe that if we are lucky, we will definitely have a great enviable future, great literature and art", his words directly apply to folklore as well (Mirziyoev, 2017).

It is known that the best customs, customs, traditions, and folk etiquette are of great importance in the development of the young generation with high moral qualities. Because whoever, from a young age, learns well the traditions of our people's life habits that have passed the test over the centuries, and listens to the teachings and teachings of our ancestors, that person will gain a high reputation in the country.

Based on these views, we want to focus on one important thing. It is known that folklore lives in harmony with all layers of people's life, and some listeners cannot even imagine it. The listener of epic, fairy tale or folk song is also the bearer of folklore. That is, folklore is alive not only with the storyteller, the storyteller, the singer, in general, the performer, but also with the listeners who are the bearers of folklore. A listener who listens to a certain folklore piece learns it, after hearing it over and over again, he develops the skills to perform certain parts of it. Even the most talented and intelligent listeners rise to the level of folklore critics, in today's phrase.

As noted in the works of our master folklorists, mature students were tested by senior poets before they were sent to write an independent epic. Together with these great poets, the listeners gave their evaluations. Therefore, as a unique feature of folklore, it is necessary to mention that the listeners participated in this creative process along with the performers-creators, and that the listeners contributed to the preservation and development of the samples of the people that have been performed and polished for centuries.

In the course of education, primary school teachers effectively use mobile teaching aids, electronic boards, audio devices, video projectors, as well as organizing excursions to the area related to the subject of the lesson, practical training in the heart of nature. was determined . A video projector is one of the modern tools used in the educational process. It requires computer hardware to use it. Pre-prepared educational materials can be presented on a special screen through a video projector connected to a computer. The materials on the computer memory or CD and regular diskettes can be shown to the students through a video projector.

A video projector, like an overhead projector, provides the highest level of presentation for the educator. The main convenience is that the provided materials can be prepared by the teacher himself on the computer or a professionally prepared electronic textbook can be used.

Simultaneous use of audio and video information increases peace of mind by 40-50%. The time required to learn a certain material is saved on average by 30%, and the acquired knowledge is stored in the memory for a long time. When multimedia technologies are used in primary school, the structure of the lesson does not change fundamentally. It still retains all of its main stages, only their timing characteristics change.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, we would like to say that in order to ensure the effectiveness

of the good work that is being carried out in the way of the formation of the spirituality of a healthy generation in our country and its further enrichment, - regardless of the field in which we work, - all of us - We are obliged.

Folklore heroes, along with living as artistic images, have also become icons and symbols representing our nation. Each of the national emblems and symbols serves to increase our national pride. Each of them is a large textbook. Man-made civilization is a stage of socio-historical development that mankind is going through, but it depends on man and mankind to make it serve the interests of man and society. The future of man-made civilization directly depends on how carefully it is applied to the educational process from the elementary grades.

In the process of education, the main task of teachers and educators is to provide education, to continuously improve students' knowledge and skills, to form their thinking, scientific outlook and ideological concepts.

In the process of moral education, the child matures morally. In the process of developing moral ideas, first of all, they begin to consciously understand their relationships with others, moral lessons develop in their relationships with peers and adults.

The traditions, lifestyle, education and cultural traditions of the Uzbek people go back to the distant centuries. The people of our current and future generations should know Uzbek national spirituality well and follow it. Only then will the society be full, prosperous, and people will live a peaceful and cultural life.

The task and content of moral education of elementary school students requires education and development of the child's spiritual world, his mind, moral feelings, personal qualities and behavior. The tasks of moral education are mainly the following:

- Education of moral feelings, ideas and behavior in children;
- Education of moral culture and positive relations;

- Education of moral feelings in a person;
- Elimination of negative feelings in behavior.

These general tasks are concretized according to age groups and are reflected in the content of the educational process. It is important to use various methods and methods in providing moral education to elementary school students.

Moral education methods are activities aimed at acquiring moral imagination and knowledge of children, cultural behavior and positive relations, moral feelings and qualities of a person. Methods of moral education are divided into such types as methods aimed at forming moral awareness, i.e. moral imagination and knowledge, the desire to fulfill them, methods aimed at forming cultural behavior and positive relations, auxiliary methods aimed at stimulating moral feelings and relations. divided.

There are also two ways of moral education.

Self-education: persuasion and self-persuasion (intellectual domain), encouragement and motivation (motivational domain), suggestion and self-hypnosis (emotional domain), demand and exercises (voluntary domain), correction and self-correction (self-regulatory domain), nurturing situations and social trials (subject-practical domain), dilemma method and reflection (existential domain).

These methods are the most effective in the process of moral education in our time. No matter how good the methods are, they only work under certain conditions.

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